

Teachers' attitude in writing research in schools of Bhutan

Bhuwan Chandra Ghalley

Damphu Central School, Tsirang, Bhutan

bcghalley@education.gov.bt

ABSTRACT

Research writing has become a need for all occupations, and teaching is no exception. Only a few instructors in Bhutan are engaged in research writing, either owing to a lack of ideas or the high burden of the job. Teachers are also encouraged to undertake research by the Ministry of Education, and each year a little sum is granted to teachers to perform research in their schools with an endowment fund. This study was undertaken to determine how many instructors are truly interested in conducting research and their research capacity. On these premises, a study was applied to assess the research capability of faculty teachers across Bhutan. It utilized descriptive, correlational, and explanatory designs. It administered survey questionnaires to 191 teachers' participants of from above two districts. Data were analyzed using descriptive and inferential statistics. According to the findings, there are just a few capable teachers who can behave themselves effectively in the field of research writing. It is possible that the explanation is due to a heavy workload and a lack of support from the school administration. The desire to undertake research is entirely dependent on their abilities as well as departmental support. The two teacher training collages do provide instruction in research writing which started few years back. The ANOVA, t-test, and correlation were used in SPSS software to obtain the results that came out to be positively significant relationship with their motivational and reward system. The interest of writing research deteriorates as the reward system shifts and the research use is not in place. The motivation to place in writing down research, the number of studies completed, and motivational reward were the determinants of research capability.

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INTRODUCTION

In Bhutan, recently the Ministry of Education (MoE) in coordination with TPSD (Teacher Professional Support Division) is seizing the study on the number of teachers who have haunted research study at school and located out that only a few teachers do have the record of concluding the education research within the country. The aim of the study was also to identify teachers and department's concerns and problems and to recommend solutions that supported the results and findings of the researches to be conducted. However, doing research by the teachers in Bhutan might not be that easy as many teachers don't seem to be equipped with the required knowledge on what research is and the way to try it. The Department of Education has been developing ways to form public school teachers knowledgeable and informed about the importance of doing research, unfortunately, many teachers were uninterested.

Teachers categorically, become researchers and have always been linked to teachers' professional development within the field of education. This is often to enable the teachers to undertake new and updated teaching strategies and modern trend pedagogies. This can help them to spot which strategy will work best during a specific classroom setting. It also addresses the learners' different needs and can help within the selection and evaluation of instructional materials for the learners' varied learning styles. There have been only a few studies within Bhutan about teachers as researchers and therefore the challenges they faced in doing research compared to other countries which have a greater number of studies. Similarly, within Bhutan, few researchers tried to look at the challenges and issues faced by the teachers in doing research. Ulla et al. (2007) supported the present trends in Bhutan educational system, doing research is very important to spot where the teachers anchor their pedagogical approaches to be utilized in the teaching and learning process. According to Quidmas (2017), to enhance the standard performance of teachers particularly in research, capacity building is incredibly important. Capacity buildings like a seminar that are challenging help do research. This may allow them to grasp more about the importance of research and have additional experiences that may help them to be more active in research writing. An article realized that professional development is taken into account to be a vehicle through which teachers are being given the possibility to boost their knowledge and skills. Within the prevalent type of professional development, research deliberates the characteristic of effective professional development which supports student learning.

In research, teachers are ready to target specific classroom needs of the learners that needed attention. It also helps teachers to critically and analytically evaluate their pedagogy and to find out the effectiveness in improving classroom practice. It should provide justification for the actions made that may be helpful for them in building repertoire, identify problems and arrive solutions for improvement (Lejarde, 2017). Consistent with Pena (2018), professional development is required for educators to beat limited applications in teaching and learning. A professional development framework is required which promotes ongoing professional development as teachers must build and acquire new knowledge to create a conceptual understanding of it. Educators should observe models and examples which seek to review instructional and develop a practical understanding of selected research. For a curricular and instructional change, educators may translate new knowledge and ideas into individual and collaborative plans. Writing research could be a factor to be considered in improving the school's curriculum for teacher researchers, schools' administrative staff, and other stakeholders within the teaching and learning environment.

The most goal of action research is to define ways on a way to enhance the lives of scholars within the education and at the identical time, to boost the lives of these professionals who are working within the tutorial systems. Research writing may be a valuable practice to undertake for teachers because it offers a collaborative, systematic, and participatory process of research that actively searches for areas of concern or redress for teachers. Additionally, writing research provides teachers with specialized knowledge and technical skills which can require influencing constructive change within classrooms, schools, and communities (Galarion, 2018). As per Marcelo (2018), research writing could be a logical process to check and collect data that may help teachers and other educational personnel to acknowledge and develop their practice. Any teacher or a school-based question, topic, or problem is vital to research and should be accustomed start the method of conducting

research. Research writing has dramatically gained support from educators, but others don't view it as a legitimate variety of research and inquiry (Anzoldo et.al, 2019). Many researchers view it as an off-the-cuff, instead of a more rigorous approach to educational approach. The sensible and limited aspect of most research, plus the fact that teachers are the first researchers ends up in distinguishing research as “applied” research instead of “true” research. It is therefore argued that while this distinction has some validity, it's also true that some research serves a very important role in improving schools. From afore cited works of literature, different points of view on research were presented to shed light on its role in education and above all to teachers. To assist teachers to upgrade and improve their skills, this study was conducted to assess the perception of writing educational researches during a public school domain.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Ferrance (2000) posited the role of administrators incorporates a great influence on school improvement and teachers' skills enhancement. Administrators help teachers by working collaboratively for his or her professional development. Additionally, earlier studies show that academic staff has to be research competent and productive. The declining research skills, knowledge, and productivity of teachers hamper the event of educational education. Papanastasiou (2005) emphasizes the event of positive attitudes towards research to reinforce teachers' capability and increase awareness. Understanding those attitudes is important to assist instructors facilitate the training of research for his or her students. The practicality of writing research, apprehension, affect signifying positive feelings about research writing, life uses of writing research to the students' day-to-day lives, and effort of research are features that were measured thus, reduces negative views on the research.

The study of Lawrence (2011) emphasized that there is a necessity to strengthen institutional support, improve research attitude and skills for better research productivity. Witchian et al. (2009) also found an instantaneous link between research productivity and therefore the characteristics of an establishment that helps enhance research competence and various attributes of an establishment that helps enhance research capability. Once teachers' research capability establishes, research productivity increases. Morales (2016) and Kutlay (2012) have similar findings which state that teaching schedule and teaching overload demotivated teachers to conduct research. Previous studies have shown that motivational factors like financial rewards, promotion, and performance enhance research skills, and Process, and research dissemination are equally important. The financial reward may be a logo of success, reinforcement and motivator, a mirrored image of one's performance, and a source of reduced anxiety. Promotion ends up in the next salary, higher social rank, better work conditions, more administrative power, more respect from colleagues and students, and other fringe benefits (Lai, 1990). The availability of adequate research support is one of the foremost essential factors in promoting research activity. Funding, ICT equipment, books/references from libraries, and also the most typical is verbal encouragement from superiors are research supports that a researcher must achieve excellent performance in research studies (Brewer, Brewer & Hilton, 2000). Formeloza and Patena (2013) determined the extent of competency in writing a probe paper, level of satisfaction with the facilities/resources provided by the institution. The results revealed that both respondents were moderately competent in terms of technical aspects and doing significant parts of the research paper also. On the opposite hand, they are satisfied with the facilities provided by the university. Plotnikoff (1995) recognized that integrating research within the teacher education curriculum includes a positive effect on teachers. Bell (2016) studies on the challenges faced in developing research competencies determined that the cantered approach encompasses a significant relationship on learners' performance as compared with the normal semester approach, and it helped in developing the research competencies within among teachers for bringing improvement academic learning.

According to Manongsong and Panopio (2018), there are several varieties of research done on factors affecting teachers' research support, effective research environment, and research capabilities. And research endeavor finds solutions and improves intellectual skills and knowledge. The supply of adequate research support in the concert of the essential factors in promoting research activity is wanting. Funding, technology, referencing books from libraries, and ICT are commonest in boosting researchers to achieve excellent

performance in research studies (Brewer, Brewer, & Hilton, 2000). On the opposite hand, researchers have also shown that research productivity depends heavily on what proportion of time one spends on research-related activities Teaching load has differential effects on research efficiency that befall across the numerous fields and groups of departmental capacities (Hancock, 1995; Wodarski, 2001).

OBJECTIVE OF THE STUDY

The objective of the study was to investigate the factor affecting the attitudes of teachers towards research writing.

METHODS

Research Design

The quantitative-descriptive research design was employed within the study. It's a way to explain and examine the attitude of the teachers in perception to research writing that may function variable within the study. The variables, in turn, are measured, typically on instruments, so that numbered data is analyzed using statistical procedures (Creswell, 2008).

Population and Sample of the Study

The teachers of the public in Bhutan were the population of the study. The questionnaires were randomly mailed to the teachers and sampling was selected as per the convenience of the researcher around the country. 191 teachers from 27 different schools all around the country are chosen as a sample to represent the population of about seven thousand teachers presently serving in different public schools of the country.

Table 1. Sampling Frame

Name of Schools	Male	Female	Total
Zhemgang LSS	9	15	24
Damphu Central School	14	29	43
Shaba High School	1		1
Mendralgang Central School	11	3	14
Lingmithang Middle Secondary School	2	2	4
Kyidsa Primary School	1		1
Norbuling Central School	2		2
Martsala Central School	6		6
Kuzugchen Middle Secondary School	2	3	5
Genekha Lower Secondary School	1	0	1
Gelephu Higher Secondary School	9	7	15
Loselling Middle Secondary School	2		2
Samtengang Central School	8	1	9
Tshangkha Central School	1	1	2
Tsheringtoed Central School	16	9	25
Sergithang Primary School	4	5	9
Tsholingkhar Primary School	8	1	9
Phuentenchu Primary School	3	1	4
Gosaling Primary School	4	2	6
Babisa High School	0	1	1
Dechencholing High School	2		2
Mothihang High School	1		1
Nganglam Central School	1		1
Norbugang Central School	1	1	1

Pakshikha Central School	1		1
Tang Central School	1		1
Zhangkhar Primary School			1
Total	111	80	191

Research Instrument

An attitude scale supported the five-point Likert technique was developed with the help of experts within the sphere. Different items of the scale were developed by studying the convenience of the teachers of Bhutan and seeking direction from current literature. Such studies as Murrey et al. (1994), Tang and Chamerlain (1997); Papanastasiou (2005); Wang and Guo (2011); Walker (2010); and Monroe and Kumar (2011) provided beacon lights within the development, improvement, and finalization of the scale. so on create sure the validity of the instrument experienced professors and experts within the sector were consulted and within the sunshine of their suggestions statements of some items were altered, the position of some items was moved, and few items were released. Pearson product-moment reliability coefficient of the size was 0.05 significant level in a hypothesis test.

Data Collection

The researcher surveyed by employing perception scale so on to hunt answers to the questions raised within the study. 200 teachers from nineteen schools were reached through e-mail, friends, and by personal contact but only data from hundred and ninety-one (191) faculty members were received and analyzed. The confidentiality was maintained without any provision to write their names. Before the collection of the data, permission was sought from school principals and District Education Officer about the conduct of the study from a different district.

Data Analysis

Data collected through an attitude questionnaire was analyzed. Scale means ratings and a five-point Likert scale were used to calculated inclinations of teachers towards different factors that affect research writing and to find out the association among different items of the factors. Items and variance of two factors were compared by calculating means, SD, Pearson values, and correlations.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The SPSS was run down on the collected data after careful study of the required component and the following are the result generated in the output and interpretation done accordingly.

Table 2. Mean and standard deviation of each factor

	N	Mean	Std. Deviation
Factor I. Research Orientation			
1. I feel professional satisfaction by conducting research.	190	3.87	.997
2. I view myself primarily as researcher	191	3.38	.903
3. I believe that Dzongkhag should support teachers who exhibit interest in research	191	4.42	.885
4. I can contribute to my school by publishing research papers that is relevant to the problem faced in my school.	190	4.09	.895

5. The intellectual challenge of academic research inspires me to work harder.	191	3.74	.505
Factor II. Reward and Influence Research			
1. I think rewards are effective means of influencing faculty performance in research.	191	4.06	.783
2. I think reward influences faculty to conduct research activities.	191	4.04	.820
3. I think faculty members must be productive researchers or stuck their promotion in future.	191	3.53	.978
4. I think that if tenure/promotions were not binding on research, most faculty would devote less time and effort to research.	190	3.69	.892
5. I can become an effective professional if I am able to have an educated critique about the quality of research.	191	4.00	.681
Factor III. Personal Interests			
1. I think that personal Interests are the most important factor in determining the allocation of time to research.	191	4.28	.727
2. I feel free to pursue my academic interests (within the context of research).	190	3.92	.762
3. I think sharing research results with colleagues is self-satisfying.	190	4.15	.666
4. I want to build up my reputation as an academic scholar through research.	189	3.92	.801
Factor IV. Mission of the School			
1. Research is a motivating factor to the mission of my school and Dzongkhag.	191	3.80	.811
2. I believe that research and teaching are mutually supportive activities.	191	4.13	.729
Factor V. Research Use			
1. In my opinion research should be mandatory for professional training.	189	3.76	.946
2. I think research is useful to every professional.	191	4.19	.760
3. In my opinion research-oriented thinking plays an important role in everyday life.	191	4.14	.720
Factor VI. Research Anxiety			
1. Research makes me nervous.	191	2.96	.956
2. Research is stressful.	191	3.42	.931
3. I feel insecure concerning the analysis of research data.	191	3.16	.862

Table 2 reveals that mean ratings of the five items of Factor-I (research orientation) ranged from 3.38 to 4.42 which shows a strong indicating inclination of school teachers towards research activities. Mean ratings of the items of Factor-II (rewards influence research) fluctuated from 3.53 to 4.06 respectively; which indicated that the reward system had a great impact on research activities inside the campuses. Score-frequency ratios of the items of Factor-III (personal interests) ranged from 3.92 to 4.28 indicating school teachers' confirmation that personal interests play an important role in carrying out research activities.

Mean ratings of the two variables in the Factor-IV (mission of school) were 3.80 and 4.13, indicating school teachers' attitudes in line with the mission of their school. Score-frequency ratios of the items of Factor-V (research use) vacillated from 3.76 to 4.19 indicating a positive attitude of faculty towards the use of research in professional and daily lives. The score-frequency ratios of the variables of Factor-VI (research anxiety) were 2.96, 3.16, and 3.42. Being less than 4, the median value, these values showed less anxiety or fear, on part of school teachers,

related to the research process and procedures. Notwithstanding that substantial population considers research as a stressful activity.

Table 3. Correlation among different factors

		Research Orientation	Rewards Influences Research	Personal Interest	Mission of the School	Research Use	Research Anxiety
F.1. Research Orientation	Pearson Correlation	1	.487**	.548**	.540**	.587**	-.224**
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.000	.000	.000	.000	.002
	N	191	191	191	191	191	191
F.2. Rewards influences Research	Pearson Correlation	.487**	1	.602**	.620**	.574**	-.028
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000		.000	.000	.000	.696
	N	191	191	191	191	191	191
F.3. Personal Interest	Pearson Correlation	.548**	.602**	1	.624**	.594**	-.094
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	.000		.000	.000	.196
	N	191	191	191	191	191	191
F.4. Mission of the school	Pearson Correlation	.540**	.620**	.624**	1	.717**	-.134
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	.000	.000		.000	.064
	N	191	191	191	191	191	191
F.5. Research Use,	Pearson Correlation	.587**	.574**	.594**	.717**	1	-.199**
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	.000	.000	.000		.006
	N	191	191	191	191	191	191
6. Research Anxiety	Pearson Correlation	-.224**	-.028	-.094	-.134	-.199**	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.002	.696	.196	.064	.006	
	N	191	191	191	191	191	191

** Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

From the above table, it is very much clear that the co-efficient correlation between research orientations with reward influences research (.748), personal interest (.548), the mission of the school (.540), and research use (.587), and research anxiety (.224). It was found to be significant at 0.01 and maybe interpreted that there exists a significant relationship of five factors with reward influence research. Teachers are influenced by the reward to carry out the research work. The rewards, which are one of the key roles in motivating teachers towards the research.

Likewise, if we look at the coefficient correlation among reward influence research, personal interest, the mission of the school, research use, and research anxiety, there does exist a significant relationship at 0.01 means there is cause and effect in the relationship integrated within six factors. These make our teacher increase their positive attitude towards writing research meaning the rewards influence our teacher to research orientation which further develops personal interest and it does fulfill the goal of the school through repeated research use and finally the research anxiety give its way after the perfection.

Figure 1. Bar graph showing the distribution of scores for each factors

Figure 1 shows the distribution of scores under each factor. In ‘*research orientation*’ (about 30%) of the teachers have the concept of how to carry out the research work but also there are small groups of teachers (below 10%) who are not aware of the research. Those teachers may be the ones who are not trained in research writing during the training in two training colleges in Bhutan. Regarding the factor ‘*reward influences research*’, there are a larger group of teachers under 30-40% which is an indication that reward is very important for carrying out the research work. They are very much concerned about rewards to research the schools either in the form of financial incentives or through acknowledgment.

The rewards are very much needed to work for research according to the teachers' respondents. The ‘*personal interest*’ and the ‘*mission of the school*’ also show greater support by the teachers with 50% in personal

interest and 80% in school mission. It is an indication that the teacher does have a personal interest in research writing and also considered the importance of research but again few teachers don't support research. Personal research interest led to achieving the mission of the school which is very much related. Next is the *use of research* and *research anxiety* which is also very much interdependent. About 60% of teachers do support the importance of research at the school but also show a higher level (about 58%) of anxiety in the conduct of the research shown by teachers. It is an indication that teachers are not confident in writing research despite having an interest and knowing the important use of the research work.

Teachers of Bhutan overall showed a positive disposition towards scholarly activities, primarily viewed themselves as researchers, felt professional satisfaction in research activities, favored the retention of only those teachers who exhibit research-creation, and contributed to their school positions through their publications by pleasing research as an academic challenge. Rewards both within the sort of intrinsic and extrinsic motivation influenced their research activities and influenced their performance. Tenure and promotion contingent upon research resulted in the devotion and efforts on a part of faculty (Khan et al., 2014). Teachers' interests determined the allocation of your time to scholarly activities; and that they felt liberal to chase their academic interests. Sharing research results with contemporaries was self-satisfying and teachers aspired to create up their reputation as instructional scholars. School faculty considered research as an interesting factor for the mission of their universities and research and teaching as mutually supportive activities. The study unearthed that university teachers considered research useful for his or her professional performance similarly as in their daily lives. The study revealed less anxiety or less fear about research by the teachers of the country. The research was neither stressful nor made them nervous, never the minor number considered it stressful. Similar results are anxiety and feeling of insecurity among teachers about research and research-related issues.

CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATION

There is a powerful orientation of school members towards research. Moreover, there is a consensus among the respondents that rewards influence research. Respondents are in perfect harmony that private interests greatly influence performance in research, which their research activities are in line with the mission of their schools. There accord among the sampled population that research is advantageous in their professional additionally as personal lives; which neither they feel any research anxiety nor it hampers their research progress notwithstanding sizeable population, particularly young school teachers, considering research as a stressful activity besides classroom teaching.

Keeping in mind the findings of the present study and within the light of conclusions drawn following recommendations are suggested: The attitude on research and inclinations towards research writing, of school teachers towards research, can be exploited by promotion of consistent research activities and provision of publication platform with the country. The school teachers who display good concert in research be properly rewarded both financially and professionally. Weightage should incline to research publications during the appointment of and promotion of the faculty. Schools should provide research opportunities during a kind of areas in each discipline, so that school teacher may involve themselves in research activities in areas of their interests. Competitive research schemes in line with the personal and specialized development of school teachers should occasionally be announced under the patronages of the Education Ministry and the Dzongkhag Education Office for optimal remunerations of research faculty. Newly appointed teacher graduate and newly inducted school teachers are provided ample opportunities of training in such vital areas of research like research planning, development of research tools, process data analysis, etc. that will motivate them to overcome the research anxiety much earlier in their profession

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